

Universidad Internacional de La Rioja
Escuela Superior de Ingeniería y Tecnología

Máster Universitario en Gestión de la Seguridad Alimentaria

**Desarrollo de un producto cárnico
saludable en relación a su contenido de
sal. Evaluación de la estimulación sensorial
en el consumidor.**

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Abstract

Health concerns and the relationship between diet and well-being highlight the need to develop foods with an improved nutritional profile. The aim of this study was to develop a reformulated meat product in the form of a low-salt hamburger, using encapsulation systems based on oil-in-water (O/W) emulsions without compromising its sensory and technological quality. The products were characterized based on their physicochemical properties (texture, color, yield, and moisture).

In addition, a sensory panel of trained judges was prepared to detect the presence of salt at different levels. Finally, an overall acceptability test was conducted for the optimized hamburgers.

The results showed that some reformulated hamburgers with encapsulated salt achieved sensory acceptability levels similar to or higher than the control samples with conventional salt levels, allowing for a sodium reduction of up to 35% without negatively affecting organoleptic properties.

It is concluded that the use of emulsions as an encapsulation system represents an effective strategy for the development of healthier meat products with reduced salt content, in line with current nutritional demands and consumer acceptance.

Keywords:

Salt reduction, Meat products, Encapsulation, Emulsion and Sensory perception.